

Job Embeddedness and Organizational Performance: The mediating roles of Social Capital and Innovative Work Behaviour

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Abstract

Organizational performance remains in the limelight of research due to the survival of organizations. There are a number of factors that contribute to organizational performance. Therefore, this research aimed to examine the impact of job embeddedness on organizational performance through social capital and innovative work behaviour as mediators in the workplace. For this purpose, the data was gathered from the 1500 respondents by using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. These respondents were working in auto-parts manufacturing firms located in different areas of Pakistan; finally 1116 questioners were considered for data analysis. Results indicate the positive impact of job embeddedness on organizational performance, as well as on social capital and innovative work behaviour in the workplace. Results also indicate the mediation of social capital between job embeddedness and organizational performance; likewise, innovative work behaviour also explains the mediation between job embeddedness and organizational performance. Interestingly, innovative work behaviour mediates the relationship between social capital and organizational performance. Pakistan is a collectivistic country where this integrated model will serve as a prerequisite for the manufacturing firms to achieve organizational performance. The future direction has also been proposed in this research.

Keywords: Job embeddedness, social capital, innovative work behaviour, organizational performance

1. Introduction

Organizational performance is one of the most debatable variables due to its legitimate concern with organizational survival. The first time organizational performance was discussed by Etzioni (1960), in which achievement and non-achievement of the organization were segregated. Majority of the focus of researchers has been on the financial performance of the organization while profitability cannot give a clear picture because generally large organizations enjoy more profitability and market share than small organizations (Hasani & O'Reilly, 2021). The organizational performance measure should be consistent with the organizational core objectives, which generally are multidimensional (Campbell & Fiske, 1959). Secondly, the characteristics also should be constant over the time period and there is a strong consensus that the core objectives of the organizations are financial performance (Eisenhardt & Zbaracki, 1992; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986; Sumarna & Muzakir, 2022), target achievement and growth (Kaplan & Norton, 1996; Hillman & Keim, 2001) and capital market performance (Dyer & Reeves, 1995). Financial performance includes return on equity, return on assets and profitability. It also includes the growth rate of stock price and market return in capital market as well. Success and growth mean the achievement of internal and external goals with the growth of employees, infrastructure and introduction of innovative products.

The previous contemporary researches are based on the contingency factors and missed to establish the relevant link of factors determining the organizational performance. The first gap in the research is that the majority of the research has missed the relevant organizational performance factors. Secondly, the majority of research studies have used cross-sectional data that is taken at one point of time. Thirdly, start of this century also brought dynamic changes around the world, which have paramount influences on the values of many societies (Murphy Gordon, & Mullen, 2004). Also the changing technological and working environment, the new findings are needed. Fourthly, economic development has transitioned from agriculture to industrial manufacturing sector and the service sector (Fuchs, 1980). The majority of research studies in Pakistan have been conducted in the service sector and unexplored the manufacturing sector. Pakistan is in a transitional phase from agriculture to the manufacturing sector. Therefore, a research in manufacturing sector is more relevant for country need and there is a need for research to find organizational performance in Pakistan with relevant factors. In Pakistan, the manufacturing sector account for 65.4% of the industrial sector, and it is on a declining trend (Farooq & Wasti, 2015). For research to generate innovative ideas, it is important that employees be open and independent to share information with a sense of equity. As in public sector an organization, the ability of employees' innovative efficiency is repressed because of the bureaucratic structure vis-à-vis the private sector (Rainey & Bozeman, 2000; Rainey, 2009; Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2012). As far as technology is concerned, Pakistan has the technologies for innovation and organizational performance. However, they are still working to innovate and develop an innovative culture. For this purpose, social capital and innovative work behaviour have a paramount role to play in achieving the desired level of organizational performance (Bhatti et al; 2012). Anxious research is needed to check the impact of job embeddedness, social capital, and innovative work behaviour on organizational performance.

The previous researches tried to establish the different antecedents of organizational performance such as turnover intention (Batt, 2002; Cheffi et al., 2021), organizational citizenship behaviour (Nielsen, Hrivnak, & Shaw, 2009; Alhashedi, Bardai, Al-Dubai, & Alaghbari, 2021), human resource management (Delery & Gupta, 2016), leadership (Iscan, Ersari & Naktiyok, 2014) etc. However, before conducting any research, it is important to know the national culture and organizational culture especially in Pakistan because organizational culture has an impact on organizational performance (Fakhar, Zahid, & Muhammad, 2013; Naveed, Alhaidan, Al Halbusi & Al-Swidi, 2022) and similarly, national culture also impacts organizational performance (Gjuraj, 2013; Pratikno et al., 2021) due to diversity of people working in an organization. Furthermore, to measure organizational performance, it is imperative that the construct should match the organizational and national culture. Pakistani culture is collectivistic where people prefer to work in groups and with families (Hofstede, 1984). Therefore, this study focus on job embeddedness, social capital and innovative work behavior as antecedents to organizational performance and the aim to examine the mediating effect of social capital and innovative work behaviour between job embeddedness and organizational performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Organizational Performance

Katz and Kahn (1978) defined organizational performance as the maximization of total returns of all types, including effectiveness, efficiency, and relevance. The contemporary focus on organizational performance is the employee's attitude and outcome (El-Ghalayini, 2017).

Different researchers have discussed multiple dimensions of organization performance since the concept being evolved. Lorsch, (1970) in the research study focused on a compatibility

between the organization and its environment, and as well with the individual contributors. In the 1970s, the concept of performance dealt with both organizational means and ends. Lupton, (1977) linked the concept of organization performance with productivity rate, level of satisfaction, employee motivation and less turnover. Katz and Kahn, (1978), simply depicted organization performance as the maximizing total returns of all kinds, which are effectiveness, efficiency, and relevancy. In 1980 concept of organization performance was related to achievement of ends and means. In 1990, the focus of organization performance remained on employee's performance (Adam, 1994). The contemporary focus on organization performance is the employee's attitude and outcome (El-Ghalayini, 2017). Ibrahim and Zulkafli, (2016) has discussed organization performance as the profitability, sales growth, sales volume and market share. Organizational performance cannot be restricted to one or two dimensions rather it is a multidimensional factor. There are couple of internal and external factors which influence the organizational performance. Among these factors the job embeddedness has gain the attention because of its composition of dimensions which has the spillover effect on the organizational performance.

2.2 Job Embeddedness

It refers to the extent to which employees believe that they are fit for their jobs, has links to other people or activities, and are willing to make sacrifices for the organization and society in order to stay in the organization (Mitchell, Holtom, Lee, Sablinski, & Erez, 2001). Job embeddedness is an emerging construct, which is a measure of individual commitment due to organizational and national factors and provides the reason of individual to stay in the organization. Job embeddedness is the links, fit and sacrifice that individual seeks. Individual's formal and informal links with society and organization fit in a job, and scarification of psychological benefits forfeited after the broken links with society or organization, determine whether he stays there or not. For organizational performance, it is important that individual must stay in the organization. Job Embeddedness is positively related to individual's performance (Mitchell et al, Ali, Shakeel, & Mujtaba, 2022) and individual performance is the determinant of organizational performance (Tatar, 2011). In this research Job embeddedness has been used as an independent variable.

In different research studies, job embeddedness has been discussed in various groups of factors like as a social, emotional, and financial, which have the kind of influences on employee wellbeing at the workplace (Mitchell et al, 2001; Yao et al, 2004; William Lee, Burch, & Mitchell, 2014). The concept of job embeddedness got popularity in 1994-95 when Mitchell et al., (2001) started a debate on why employees stay with the organization, as job embeddedness is the collection those factors that influence the employee retention (Mitchell et al, 2001; Lee et al, 2004). Lee et al., (2004) first time tested the job embeddedness to predict job performance and organizational citizenship behaviour. They concluded that job embeddedness has a positive impact on organizational citizenship behaviour and individual performance.

2.3 Job embeddedness and organizational performance

Job embeddedness has shown a positive relationship with organizational performance by improving individual performance. Job embeddedness studies have been done world over and proved a significant relationship with performance (Nafei, 2015; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008; Sekiguchi, Burton & Sablinski, 2008; Sun et al., 2011; Karatepe, 2016; Wijayanto & Kismono, 2004; Lev and Koslowsky, 2012). All these studies have been done in a different culture and focusing different dimensions of the organizational performance. This study has been designed first time to cover the most relevant dimensions of organizational performance as a single construct and in Pakistani culture. Therefore, the following hypothesis has drawn to check the state of job embeddedness and organizational performance:

H₁: There is a positive impact of Job embeddedness on organizational performance

2.3 Job embeddedness and social capital

It refers to networks of employees at the workplace in the organization, with the extent of social relations, shared values and understanding with each other, trust, and supportive behaviour for innovative collaboration (Cohen & Prusak, 2001).

Job embeddedness due to its multi-applicability has shown its multiple effects. Since job embeddedness encompasses factors from both on-the-job and off-the-job that explain more exclusively about individual's relationship. The study done by Ng & Feldman, (2010) has built a relationship of job embeddedness with social capital. Due to Job embeddedness individual feels more embedded with the job due to fit in organization and community, having links with the organization and society and scarifying the cost of having a relationship with the organization and the community. With the application of job embeddedness theory, social capital increases (Holtom, Mitchell, & Lee, 2006) that further keeps the individual embedded with the job. Henceforth, the following hypothesis explains the relationship of job embeddedness and social capital:

H₂: There is a positive impact of job embeddedness on social capital

2.4 Job embeddedness and innovative work behaviour

Innovative work behaviour is the application of cognition to generate new ideas for the creation of a new procedure, new product, or new service that will benefit the individual, the organization, or all stakeholders. This can be done alone or in collaboration with certain external factors (Carmeli, Meitar & Weisberg, 2006).

The employees who stay committed over the long duration to their job, they are more to show innovative work behaviour or and keep coming up with innovation at the workplace (Choi & Price, 2005). In two different studies done depict that when a human being feels appreciated within the business, they show a sense of faithfulness to the peeling of new ideas in their work and these new ideas may be translated into innovation (Eisenberger, Fasolo, & Davis, 1990) and (Noefer, Stegmaier, Molter, & Sonntag, 2009). Therefore, for further understanding about job embeddedness, there is need to explore more of the job embeddedness (Ghosh & Gurunathan, 2015) and its relationship with innovative work behavior. Hence, the following hypothesis has drawn to explain the relationship:

H₃: There is a positive impact of Job embeddedness on innovative work behaviour

2.5 Social capital and organizational performance

Social capital (Hanifan, 1916) compasses the social relations, supportive culture, knowing and understanding each other, shared values and innovative collaboration of the employees at workplace. Social capital consists of three dimensions: a) cognition dimension which comprises of common language, vision and shared codes and these are practices at the workplace, b) structural dimension that constitutes the social relations and boundness among the employees, c) relational dimension which is entirely ready of help, group identity, openness to sharing and criticism. All of these dimensions have the relationship of with the number of organizational goals and managers use social capital to retain their employees to achieve better performance (Yi-Renko et al., 2001; Chua, 2002; Hysman & De Wit, 2004). Due to social connection and interpersonal relationship employees gain more knowledge and access to valuable resources (Adler & Kwon, 2002; Coleman, 1988). This social capitalization enhance formal and informal value of the individual as well as the organization itself (Coleman, 1990; Leana & Van Buren, 1999; Oh, Labianca & Chung, 2006) in term of improved organizational outcomes such as organizational performance (Pil & Leana, 2009). Thus, the following hypothesis proposed to explain the relationship:

H₄: There is a positive impact of social capital on organizational performance

2.6 Social capital and innovative work behaviour

As social capital refers to the total of possible resources rooted in an individual's joint network at work (Bourdieu, 1980), this sum of social capital can be used to acquire new skills and expand one's knowledge base in order to gain multiple benefits and achieve goals (Chen & Beaudoin, 2016). Therefore, some researchers highlight that social capital can contribute to promoting technological innovation through innovative work behaviour (Scott & Bruce 1994, 1998), which further leads to increasing innovative competitiveness (Ng & Law, 2015). When the organizations have more connections in the network, then it enables the organizations to get essential knowledge. Looking for and gathering information from these connections speeds up the process of developing innovative work behaviour (Akhavan & Hosseini, 2015). Yli-Renko et al. (2001) studied British enterprises and found that social capital helps in acquiring essential customer knowledge and enables the organizations to do further targeted innovation. The social capital of the organization can influence the behaviour of the employees in ways that lead to innovative work behaviour. Thus, the following hypothesis is generated to examine the state of the relationship:

H₅: There is a positive impact of social capital on innovative work behaviour

2.7 Innovative work behaviour and organizational performance

Innovative work behaviour (Scott & Bruce 1994, 1998) is one of the important construct that is the antecedent of individual's innovation leads to organizational performance. Innovative work behaviour is the intended behaviour of the individual to share and introduce new ideas, work processes, procedures and products to the relevant department of adoption, considerably benefit the individual, the group, organization or society at large (De Jong, 2007). As an attitudinal variable, innovative work behaviour is inclined to internal and external factors. Innovative work behaviour as an independent variable has shown a significant relationship (De Jong, & Den Hartog, 2010). Leong and Rasli (2014) in Malaysian manufacturing firm found a strong association of innovative work behaviour with performance. Another study by Bysted, (2013) further endorsed the significant impact of innovative work behaviour on performance. Due to innovative work behaviour individual explores new ideas and methods to bring innovation in the process and products which eventually translate into organizational performance. Innovative work behaviour and job performance are imperative for organizations to cultivate more fundamental competitiveness and safeguard survival in this disruptive world (Deng, Liu, Yang & Duan, 2022). Hence,

H₆: There is a positive impact of Innovative work behaviour on organizational performance

2.8 Social capital as a mediator between job embeddedness and organizational performance:

In this particular research, first time social capital has been used as a mediating variable between job embeddedness and organizational performance due to its more effective placement with the independent and dependent variables. The social capital mediating effect has already been tested in many constructs, and it has proved its significance. Social capital mediates the relationship between a high-performance work system and effectiveness (Jiang et al, 2015). In another study, social capital mediated the relationship between open innovation and firm performance (Rass et al., 2013). Social capital is the social networking of individuals that gives them a chance to build a relationship but also an opportunity to share ideas that improve organizational performance because those individuals who are good in social capital have a positive influence on their innovative work behaviour (Mura et al., 2012). A study in small medium enterprises (SMEs) also confirmed that social capital enhances innovative work behaviour (Xerri & Brunetto, 2011). Social capital provides this opportunity for individuals to

share ideas and bring innovation. Therefore, the following hypothesis explains the intended relationship:

H7: Social capital has the mediating relationship between the job embeddedness and innovative organizational performance

2.9 Innovative work behaviour as a mediator between job embeddedness and organizational performance

The research was expanded on job embeddedness, when Sekiguchi et al. (2008) reasoned the use of job embeddedness as a moderating variable between leader-member exchange (LMX) and contextual factors. Wheeler et al., (2012) and Lev and Koslowsky (2012) further extended the research to use job embeddedness as a mediating variable. Further studies revealed the mediating relationship of job embeddedness between intentions to leave by the employees and four functions of human resource management: supervisory support, training, compensation, and growth opportunity (Bergiel, Nguyen, Clenney, & Taylor, 2009). Later, when Ng and Feldman (2010) conducted research on job embeddedness in relation to innovation and social capital, the other aspect of job embeddedness was explored. They found that job embeddedness helps to reduce employee turnover because job embeddedness helps in reducing employees turnover and more job-embedded employees show further innovative work behaviour. As a result, job embeddedness positively influences innovative work behaviour because of a lower intention to leave the job (Widianto et al., 2012). Hence, the following hypothesis is intended to explain the relationship:

H8: Innovative work behaviour has a mediating relationship between the job embeddedness and organizational performance.

2.10 Innovative work behaviour as a mediator between social capital and organizational performance

It is important to note that social capital affects innovative work behaviour and innovative work behaviour has a positive link with organizational performance. Social capital" delivers interaction for innovative collaboration among employees (Sözbilir, 2018). It has positive effects on knowledge sharing and intellectual capital, which has an eventual effect on innovation and also performance (Allameh, 2018). It provides the reason for innovative work behaviour to be used as a mediating variable between social capital and organizational performance. The mediation of innovative work behaviour between social capital and organizational performance is another addition to the literature.

H9: Innovative work behaviour has a mediating relationship between the social capital and organizational performance.

Figure 1: Theoretical Research Model

3. Methodology

3.1 Sampling and Data Collection Procedure

The data was collected from respondents working in auto-parts manufacturing business corporations located in the cities of Lahore, Gujranwala, Islamabad, and Rawalpindi. Respondents were selected by using the non-probability purposive sampling technique. A total of 1500 questionnaires were distributed by the lead persons, and courier services to collect primary data. Further, the data acquisition process was also done through emails, phone calls, WhatsApp, and personal visits. At the end of the survey, a total of 1336 questionnaires were received back. During the data screening process, 220 research questionnaires were excluded from data analysis because these questionnaires were not properly filled out by the respondents. Finally, it was observed that 1116 questionnaires were error-free and usable for this research purpose. In order to control social desirability bias to some extent, the volunteer focal persons were appointed to administer the questionnaires among the targeted respondents. The respondents were briefed in organized sessions on how to fill out the questionnaire and also control their perceived biases. All the respondents were ensured that their identity would be disclosed anywhere at any time. Even in the questionnaire, there was no such mark that directly or indirectly pointed out any of the respondents. Therefore, respondents were pretty confident in filling out the questionnaire. The respondents were also told that their views on IWB items would be validated by their respective managers, which was eventually done after getting the questionnaire from the respondents.

3.2 Research instrument

A self-administrative questionnaire was used as a survey instrument. This questionnaire has two parts:

3.2.1 Part I- Demographics of respondents

Part I consists of questions related to the demographics of respondents. For example, the questions are age, gender, income level, qualification, marital status, family system, nature of the job, and native area.

3.2.2 Part I- Variables items & scale

Part II consists of item questions related to study variables, and these items of constructs were measured on five point Likert scale from 1= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree. The job embeddedness (JE) has 18 items, which were taken from Holtom, Mitchell, & Lee, (2006) ($\alpha = .85$). A few items related to JE are; *a. My job utilizes my skills and talents well, b. I feel like I am a good match for my organization, c. I really love the place where I live.* The 15-item scale of social capital (SC) ($=.81$) was used to measure social capital responsiveness, which was originally developed by Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) and used by (Andrews, 2010; Miller; 1983; Cusack; 1999; Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998). *The few items of social capital are; a. In this department, we respect each other's competencies, b. In this department, every worker shows integrity, c. In this department, we expect the complete truth from each other.* Janssen (2000) developed the 12 item scale ($=.87$) for innovative work behaviour (IWB), which was later used in other research studies (Mukherjee & Ray, 2009; Kheng, June, & Mahmood, 2013). The sample items of IWB are; *a. In our department, I create new ideas for difficult issues, b. In our department I search out new work methods, techniques, or instruments, c. In our department, I generate original solutions for problems.* Organizational performance (OP) 15 items scale was used 5 items ($\alpha = .83$) were taken from (Smith & Blum, 2000) and 10 from Adams, 1963; 1965, Ostrom, 1975 and later used by Carton and Hofer (2006) items includes such as; a. the products quality, b. the capability to attract competent employees, and relations between management and employees. In last couple of years, there has been an increasing tendency to

use these items for the rating of supervisor competencies of supervisors (Arentsen et al, 2021; Yuan & Woodman, 2010; Zhang & Bartol, 2010). For IWB, another segment of a poll of questions was developed, and organizational performance was rated by the supervisor. All the items were in English because of a common understanding of the language, and respondents filled out the questionnaires without any ambiguity, as used previously (Butt & Choi, 2006). Questionnaires were filled in by respondents through self-administration wherever possible, and also used digital means to get filled in questionnaires from respondents with certain follow-ups.

4. Results

4.1 Respondents Characterizes

Among the respondents there was 78% male (n = 870), and 22 % being female (n = 246); and in the age category, 28.5% were between the age of 21 and 25 years, 22.4% were the 26 to 30 years' age group, 21.5% were the age of 31 and 35 accounted and 1% of above the age of 45. In education category, 39.8% respondents were O'Level/10th standard: (n = 444), then A-level/12th standard: 18.6% (n = 208), diploma holders were the 6.4% (n=71), 15% were abstained the 14years of educational degree (n=167), 16years of master education were the 14.3% (n=160), 4.3% were the engineers (n=48) and 1.6% were the PhDs (n=18). The qualification confirmed that all the respondents were qualified to understand the importance of this research. In job positions, 26% respondents were holding managerial job (n=290) while 74% non-managerial (n=826). In the income level category 40.5% respondents were having less than Rs.20,000 per month (n=452), 33.81% respondents were second highest number was from Rs.20,000 to Rs.30,000 (n=377) of their income level, 3.4% respondents' had the salary range from Rs.31,000 to Rs.40,000 (n=38), 12.5% respondents were Rs.41,000 to Rs.50,000 (n=140), 7.8% respondents were Rs.51,000 to Rs.60,000 (n=87), 0.9% respondents were Rs.61,000 to Rs.80,000 (n=10), 0.4% respondents were Rs.81,000 to Rs.100,000 (n=4), and 0.7% were above 100,000, n=8). Whereas in the work experience category 45.6 % respondents had less than one year of experience (n=509), 39.9% had experience from 01 to 05 years (n=445), 6.8% from 06 to 10 years of experience (n=76) and 7.7% had above 11 years of experience (n=86).

The factor, validity analyses and procedural rectification were conducted to reduce and safeguard the common bias method (CMB). In previous classical studies, the issue of self-reporting measures has been highlighted with cross-sectional designed studies (Podsakoff et al., 2003). For IWB and OP measures, supervisor's rating part of the questionnaire was added. Harman's single factor (HSF) test is frequently used method to know the CMB (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The results of HSF test shown that among all items of questionnaire there is 62% variance, which reside in the acceptable range. Table 01 shows the value of chi-square which is statically significant at 95% confidence level, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy is > 0.60 and the Eigenvalue (EV) was above 1.0. This result evidently shows the measures inherit validity of the construct. For each construct principal component analysis was applied as shown in table -1. The Factor loading of 15 items of OP construct shows the value of KMO (0.72) that comes within satisfactory level whereas EV is > 1 with 56% variance of same construct. For job embeddedness (JE) the value of KMO is 0.78 which is also at acceptable point. The JE 18 items construct the value of EV >1 with the variation of 47%. SC nine items shows the value of KMO is 0.65 which is also acceptable and the value of EV is >1 with the variation of 51%. Likewise, the IWB 12 items scale has KMO value is 0.87, with the EV value > .6 and this reside in acceptable range. EV value for IWB is again >1 and explained a variation of 47% in IWB construct. The value of factor loading of OP 15 items

was compatible with Smith and Blum, (2000) and Carton (2004) research studies. Table 1 exhibit the values of all constructs which are within acceptable range. Likewise the values of Cronbach's alpha for all constructs are $>.6$, this value is also acceptable (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Table. 1 Factor Analysis

Variables	Items	Factor (s)	KMO Test	X2	Eigen value (EV)	Variation	α
Organizational Performance (OP)	15	1	.72	2410*	1.02	56%	.67
Job Embeddedness (JE)	18	1	.78	3805*	1.9	47%	.68
Social Capital (SC)	9	1	.65	1520*	1.13	51%	.67
Innovative Work Behaviour (IWB)	12	1	.87	3208*	1.6	47%	.82

n=1116. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy. ** $p<0.01$; * $p<0.05$

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The detail results of correlation exhibited in table 2, JE as an independent variable has the significant positive relationship with the OP ($r=.114$, $p<0.01$), mediating variable SC ($r=.136$, $p<0.01$) and second mediating variable IWB ($r=.118$, $p<0.01$). Correlation of SC and OP is ($r=.154$, $p<0.01$) that tells the strong association of SC and OP. SC relationship with IWB is significant ($r=.206$, $p<0.01$). The relationship of IWB with OP is also positive and significant ($r=.185$, $p<0.01$). Table 2 clearly highlights that all variable has a strong association with each other.

Table. 2 Correlation among the variables

Variables	M	S.D	OP	JE	SC	IWB
OP	3.59	.42	1			
JE	3.62	.41	.114**	1		
SC	3.72	.46	.154**	.136**	1	
IWB	3.65	.62	.185**	.118**	.206**	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed)

4.3 Regression Analysis

Table 3 exhibits the results of regression analysis. This shows the value of regression model which is significant, $F= 16.69$, $P<.001$. This reveals that JE has the significant impact on OP at work place. Moreover, as an independent variable JE is also significant β -value ($\beta=.117$) with OP as dependent variable. The R^2 ($R^2=.012$) of the JE value also shows the significant change. It means the one unit of increased in JE ($\beta = 0.117$, $p <.001$) would lead 0.117 units increased in OP. Therefore, hypothesis that there is positive impact of JE on OP has supported and is accepted.

Table. 3 Regression Analysis of Job Embeddedness and Organizational Performance

Job Embeddedness (JE)					
	β	R^2	t	F	Sig
Job Embeddedness(JE) as (IV)	0.117**	0.012	3.83	16.69	0.000

Organizational Performance (Dependent Variable). *** $p<.001$, ** $p<.005$, * $p<.01$

The β -value ($\beta=.155$) of JE is significant as an independent variable and while SC is the dependent variable in relation to JE. Also there is a significant change in R^2 ($R^2=.018$) of JE. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is the positive impact of JE on SC has supported and is accepted.

Table. 4 Regression Analysis of Job Embeddedness and Social Capital

Job Embeddedness(JE)					
	β	R^2	t	F	Sig
Job Embeddedness(JE) as (IV)	0.155**	0.018	4.59	21.09	0.000

Social Capital (Dependent Variable).*** $p < .001$, ** $p < .005$, * $p < .01$

Table 5 exhibits the results of regression analysis. This shows the value of regression model which is significant, $F=15.65$, $P < .001$. This reveals that JE has the significant impact on IWB at work place. Moreover, as an independent variable JE is also significant β -value ($\beta=.117$) with IWB as dependent variable. The R^2 ($R^2=.013$) of the JE value also shows the significant change. Therefore, hypothesis that there is positive impact of JE on IWB has supported and is accepted.

Table. 5 Regression Analysis of Job Embeddedness and Innovative Work Behaviour

Job Embeddedness(JE)					
	β	R^2	t	F	Sig
Job Embeddedness(JE) as (IV)	0.177**	0.013	3.96	15.65	0.000

Innovative Work Behaviour (Dependent Variable).*** $p < .001$, ** $p < .005$, * $p < .01$

Table 6 exhibits the results of regression analysis. This shows the value of regression model which is significant, $F=49.23$, $P < .001$. This reveals that SC has the significant impact on IWB at work place. Moreover, as an independent variable JE is also significant β -value ($\beta=.274$) with IWB as dependent variable. The R^2 ($R^2=.042$) of the JE value also shows the significant change. Therefore, hypothesis that there is positive impact of SC on IWB has supported and is accepted.

Table. 6 Regression Analysis of Social Capital and Innovative Work Behaviour

Social Capital(SC)					
	β	R^2	t	F	Sig
Social capital(SC) as (IV)	0.274**	0.042	7.02	49.23	0.000

Innovative Work Behaviour (Dependent Variable) *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .005$, * $p < .01$

Table 7 exhibits the results of regression analysis. This shows the value of regression model which is significant, $F=39.65$, $P < .001$. This reveals that IWB has the significant impact on OP at work place. Moreover, as an independent variable JE is also significant β -value ($\beta=.126$)

with OP as dependent variable. The R^2 ($R^2=.034$) of the JE value also shows the significant change. Therefore, hypothesis that there is positive impact of IWB on OP has supported and is accepted.

Table. 7 Regression Analysis of Innovative Work Behaviour and Organizational Performance

Innovative Work Behaviour (IWB)					
	B	R ²	t	F	Sig
Innovative Work Behaviour (IWB) as (IV)	0.126**	0.034	6.29	39.65	0.000

*Organizational Performance (Dependent Variable) ***p<.001, **p<.005, *p<.01*

In behaviour research, the Hayes Bootstrap is the reliable technique being used by the researchers. In this research study, the bootstrapping procedure was repeated with 1000 samples. The mediator will be considered significant at 95% confidence interval (CI) if there is no zero value between the low-level confidence interval (LLCI) and Upper-level confidence interval (ULCI) (Preacher & Hayes, 2004). A path analysis was carried to check the mediation effect of both SC and IWB. Table 08 shows the results of 1,000 bootstrapped samples with the *total effect = 0.1172, p = 0.001*; *direct effect is = 0.0975., p = 0.0015* and indirect effect of SC as a mediator were significant, while the indirect effect is =.0197. In all direct and indirect cases the *p* is <.05, which shows the mediation of selected variables. The results specify that there is the mediation of SC between JE and OP because the direct effect of JE on OP was reduced in indirect effect through SC. There is no zero between lower 95 % *CI = 0.0093*, upper 95 % *CI = .0353*. This result evidently shows that due to SC mediation, there is the rise IWB. Therefore, the hypothesis that Social capital has the mediating relationship between the job Embeddedness and organizational performance is accepted.

Moreover, the results also show the significant mediating effect of IWB with (*total effect = 0.1172, p = 0.001*; *direct effect = 0.0961., p = 0.016*), and the indirect effect = 0.0211. It means IWB mediates between JE and OP because the indirect effect of IWB cause in reduction of the direct effect of JE on OP. This also confirmed through that there is no zero value between the lower 95 % *CI = 0.0099* and upper 95 % *CI = .0370*. Result evidently shows that due to SC mediation, IWB is enhanced. Therefore, the hypothesis that IWB has the mediating relationship job Embeddedness and organizational performance is accepted.

Table. 8 Mediating Effects of JE, SC, IWB, and OP

Path	Total Effect	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	95% CI	
				Low Level	Upper level
JE → SC → OP	.1172 (0.0001)	.0975 (0.0015)	.0197 (.002)	.0093	.0353
JE → IWB → OP	.1172 (0.0001)	.0961 (0.0016)	.0211 (.001)	.0099	.0370
SC → IWB → OP	.1394 (0.0000)	.1095 (0.0001)	.0299 (.001)	.0170	.0470

JE=Job embeddedness, SC=Social capital, IWB= Innovative work behaviour, OP= Organizational performance

Moreover, the results also show the significant mediating effect of IWB with (*total effect* = 0.1394, $p = 0.001$; *direct effect* = 0.1095., $p = 0.0001$), and the indirect effect = 0.0299. It means IWB mediates between SC and OP because the indirect effect of IWB cause in reduction of the direct effect of JE on OP. This also confirmed through that there is no zero value between the lower 95 % *CI* = 0.0170 and upper 95 % *CI* = .0470. Result evidently shows that due to SC mediation, IWB is enhanced. Therefore, the hypothesis that IWB has the mediating relationship SC and OP is accepted.

5. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of job embeddedness on performance with a mediating effect of social capital and innovative work behaviour in the auto manufacturing sector of Pakistan. To our knowledge, no published paper has examined this specific integrated model by focusing on the auto manufacturing sector. Drawing on social exchange theory, we conceptually argue that studying SC and IWB as mediating between JE and JP might add candid insights to the existing body of literature. Therefore, in line with the aforementioned results, this research fills the gap in the existing literature. The results of the research indicate that job embeddedness (JE) has a positive impact on organizational performance (OP). Both on-the-job and off-the-job JE factors keep employees in the auto manufacturing sector loyal to the company and gain a better understanding of the products and processes that result in a competitive advantage and OP. Similar studies in different parts of the world endorse the same results (Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008; Karatepe & Karadaş, 2012; Sekiguchi, Burton, & Sablynski, 2008; Sun et al., 2011; Nafei, 2015). It is also worth noting that JE has a positive impact on social capital (SC) because employees with a greater sense of fit and link, create more socialization within the organization because they think getting into a working relationship is more beneficial than its cost, which also confirms the notion of social exchange theory that highlights a person wants to be part of a social network if it is more beneficial than its cost. In this research, SC has been used as a mediating variable. For mediation, it is important that the independent variable should have an impact on the mediating variable when used as a dependent variable. Due to JE, the employee feels fit in the organization and the community, and it enhances SC, which is the networking and relationships of individuals. This also makes the employees collaborate for the betterment of the organization. Similar studies confirm this relationship (Ng & Feldman, 2010; Holtom, Mitchell, & Lee, 2006). It is also reflected that in the workplace, the JE has a positive impact on innovative work behaviour (IWB). In this research, IWB is a second mediating variable. Due to JE, individuals remain with the organization and there is less turnover intention and involvement in IWB because JE has become prominent in contemporary turnover literature since it is more than the job satisfaction and commitment theories, which have more focus on individual jobs. Therefore, more embedded with the organization, employees possess more information about the company and would be able to generate more SC and extend the IWB. More experienced workers are more innovative (Choi & Price, 2005). Results revealed that SC has a positive impact on OP because more networking and relationships give an opportunity for employees to share ideas and information to enhance OP (Rass et al., 2013). SC also enhances IWB due to the sharing of ideas and information in a formal and informal way (Mura et al., 2012; Xerri & Brunetto, 2011). Results also reflect that IWB has a positive impact on OP. It is obvious that an individual's IWB would bring positive change in process and product that ultimately enhances OP (Bysted, 2013). Therefore, it is important that managers of auto manufacturers provide a conducive environment for their employees to collaborate for more innovativeness. This integrated model provides the rational use of all variables to determine the impact of independent variables on dependent and mediating variables. The novelty of this model is the use of all variables in a rational manner that has not been used before. This study

was conducted in Pakistani culture, which is different from the other cultures of the west, where previous research studies were conducted. The research was done in engineering manufacturing firms that were declining due to innovation and the performance was the cause of concern.

5.1 Theoretical implications

This study connected the missing gap in the literature in many ways. First, this research study proposed an integrated model to provide a better understanding of job embeddedness in relation to organizational performance from the perspective of social exchange theory. Second, the findings add to the body of knowledge that social capital and innovative work behaviour act as a bridge to transmit job embeddedness characteristics to organizational performance because deep involvement in the job helps the employees to come up with new ideas and apply during the course of the job as suggested by Lambe, Wittmann, & Spekman (2001). Thirdly, it better explains the relationship between an individual and an organization because research has shifted from functional human resource management to employee behaviour to investigate avenues for organizational improvement. Further, this integrated model was empirically tested in the manufacturing sector, in particular, the auto parts manufacturer, from a research perspective, as the manufacturing sector is more prone to job embeddedness, social capital, and innovative work behaviour with reference to organizational performance. Lastly, the overall integrated model tested in the auto parts manufacturing firm is a new addition in the management discipline.

5.2 Managerial implications

The managerial implications of this research study suggest that managers must enhance the feelings of job embeddedness, related to the factors of being on-the-job and off-the-job. Managers in auto parts manufacturing will be sensitized that enhanced job embeddedness would help in reduction of the turnover of employees, which will benefit organizations by saving the cost of recruiting and training. Therefore, it is important to understand the paramount importance of JE and its benefits in many folds. Also managers would provide opportunities for employees to share ideas and develop relationships through social capital will increase their innovative work behaviour, allowing them to develop any new product or process and, ultimately, improve organizational performance. Similarly, managers need to design the training to realize the employees that the training is beneficial for them not for the organization, otherwise without the keen interest of employees in training will increase the cost of the organization not the innovative work behaviour and organizational performance.

5.3 Limitations and Future Recommendations

There are few limitations of this study. The first limitation is the data collected from 26 companies only while there are 400 companies. Secondly, the data collected was from small and big firms collectively. There is a need to get data separately from large and small firms and a comparative research should be done. The research focus was on private and in engineering manufacturing sector. The research focus should be in public and other sectors to find the overall results of the variables. For future purposes, the personality traits should be used as mediating variables between JE and OP. Personality traits vary and will tell which trait is more oriented towards performance with JE. Similarly, the demographic variables like regional native areas such as rural or urban may also be the option as independent variables to find OP with mediating variable SC. It will tell the mediating effect of SC with Urban or rural areas.

References

- Adam, E.E., (1994). Alternative quality improvement practices and organization performance. *Journal of Operations Management*, 12(1), 27-44.

- Adams, J. S. (1963). Towards an Understanding of Inequality. *Journal of Abnormal and Normal Social Psychology*, 67 (5), 422-436.
- Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequality in Social Exchange, in *Advances in Experimental Psychology*. L. Berkowitz (ed). Academic Press, New York.
- Adler, P. S., & Kwon, S. W. (2002). Social capital: Prospects for a new concept. *Academy Of Management Review*, 27(1), 17-40.
- Akhavan, P.; Hosseini, S.M (2015). Social capital, knowledge sharing, and innovation capability: an empirical study of R&D teams in Iran. *Technol. Anal. Strateg. Manag*, 28, 96–113.
- Alhashedi, A. A. A., Bardai, B., Al-Dubai, M. M. M., & Alaghbari, M. A. (2021). Organizational citizenship behavior behaviour role in mediating the effect of transformational leadership on organizational performance in gold industry of Saudi Arabia. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 22(1), 39-54.
- Ali, I., Khan, M. M., Shakeel, S., & Mujtaba, B. G. (2022). Impact of psychological capital on performance of public hospital nurses: The mediated role of job embeddedness. *Public Organization Review*, 22(1), 135-154.
- Allameh, S. M. (2018). Antecedents and consequences of intellectual capital: The role of social capital, knowledge sharing and innovation. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 19 (5), 2-18.
- Andrew, R. (2010). Organizational Social Capital, Structure and Performance. *Human Relations*, 63(5), 583-608.
- Arentsen, T. J., Clements, M., Meier, A. M., Pannell, L., & Putman, K. M. (2021). Multisource evaluation of policing competence: the development of self-and supervisor-rating scales for police recruits. *Police Practice and Research*, 1-17.
- Batt, R. (2002). Managing customer services: Human resource practices, quit rates, and sales growth. *Academy of Management Journal*, 45, 587–597.
- Bergiel, E. B., Nguyen, V. Q., Clenney, B. F., & Taylor, G.S. (2009). Human resource practices, job embeddedness and intention to quit. *Management Research News*, 32(3), 205-219.
- Bourdieu, P. Le (1980) Capital Social: Notes Provisoires. *Actes Rech. Sci. Soc*, 31, 2–3.
- Butt, A. N., & Choi, J. N. (2006). The effects of cognitive appraisal and emotion on social motive and negotiation behavior behaviour: The critical role of agency of negotiator emotion. *Human Performance*, 19(4), 305-325.
- Bysted, R. (2013). Innovative employee behaviour: The moderating effects of mental involvement and job satisfaction on contextual variables. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 16(3), 268-284.
- Campbell, D. T., & Fiske, D. W. (1959). Convergent and discriminant validation by the multitrait-multimethod matrix. *Psychological bulletin*, 56(2), 81.
- Carmeli, A., Meitar, R., & Weisberg, J. (2006). Self-leadership skills and innovative behavior at work. *International Journal of Manpower*, 27(1), 75-90
- Carton, R. B. & Hofer, C. W. (2006) *Measuring Organizational Performance: Metrics for Entrepreneurship and Strategic Management Research*, Northampton, MA: Edgard Elgar Publishing.
- Cheffi, W., Malesios, C., Abdel-Maksoud, A., Abdennadher, S., & Dey, P. (2021). Corporate social responsibility antecedents and practices as a path to enhance organizational performance: The case of small and medium sized enterprises in an emerging economy country. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(6), 1647-1663.
- Chen, H.; Beaudoin, C.E. (2016). An empirical study of a social network site: Exploring the effects of social capital and information disclosure. *Telemat. Inf.*, 33, 432–435.

- Choi, J. N. & Price, R. H. (2005). The effects of person-innovation fit on individual responses to innovation. *Journal of Occupational & Organizational Psychology*, 78(1), 83–96.
- Chua, A. (2002). The influence of social interaction on knowledge creation. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 3(4), 375 – 392.
- Cohen, D., & Prusak, L. (2001). In good company: How social capital makes organizations work: Harvard Business Press.
- Coleman, J. S. (1988). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American Journal of Sociology*, 94, S95-S120.
- Coleman, J. S. (1990). *Foundations of Social Theory* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1990)
- Cusack, T. R. (1999). Social Capital, Institutional Structures, and Democratic Performance: A Comparative Study of German Local Governments. *European Journal of Political Research*, 35, 1-34.
- De Jong, J. (2007). Individual innovation: The connection between leadership and employees' innovative work behavior. PhD University of Twente, EIM: Zoetermeer.
- De Jong, J.P.J. & Den Hartog, D.N. (2010). Measuring innovative work behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 19(1), 23-26.
- Delery, J., & Gupta, N. (2016). Human resource management practices and organizational effectiveness: internal fit matters. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, 3 (2), 139-163.
- Deng, J., Liu, J., Yang, T., & Duan, C. (2022). Behavioural and economic impacts of end-user computing satisfaction: Innovative work behaviour and job performance of employees. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 107367.
- Dyer, L., & Reeves, T. (1995). Human resource strategies and firm performance: what do we know and where do we need to go?. *International Journal of human resource management*, 6(3), 656-670.
- Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., & Davis, L.V. (1990). Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Diligence, Commitment, and Innovation. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 75 (1), 51-59.
- Eisenhardt, K. & Zbaracki, M. (1992). Strategic Decision Making. *Strategic Management Journal*, 13, 17-37.
- El-Ghalayini, Y. (2017). Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Performance in Public Sector Organization. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 8(3), 65-80.
- Etzioni, A. (1960). Two approaches to organizational analysis: A critique and a suggestion. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 257-278.
- Shahzad, F., Iqbal, Z., & Gulzar, M. (2013). Impact of organizational culture on employees job performance: An empirical study of software houses in Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 5(2), 56-64.
- Fuchs, V. R. (1980). *Economic growth and the rise of service employment*: National Bureau of Economic Research Cambridge, Mass., USA.
- Ghosh, D., & Gurunathan, L. (2015). Job Embeddedness: A Ten-year Literature Review and Proposed Guidelines. *Global Business Review*, 16(5), 856-866.
- Gjuraj, E. (2013). The importance of national culture studies in the organizational context. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(11), 160-180
- Halbesleben, J.R.B., & Wheeler, A.R. (2008). The relative roles of engagement and embeddedness in predicting job performance and intentions to leave. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 242–256.
- Hanifan, L. J. (1916) The rural school community center *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 67:130-138.

- Hasani, T. and O'Reilly, N. (2021), Analyzing antecedents affecting the organizational performance of start-up businesses, *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 13 1, 107-130.
- Hillman, A., & Keim, G. (2001). Shareholder value, stakeholder management, and social issues: What's the bottom line? *Strategic Management Journal*, 22, 125-139.
- Hofstede, G. (1984). *Culture's consequences: International differences in work-related values* (Vol. 5): Sage
- Holtom B.C., Mitchell T.R., & Lee T.W. (2006). Increasing human and social capital by applying job embeddedness theory. *Organizational Dynamics*, 35(4), 316–331
- Huysman, M., & De Wit, D. (2004). Practices of managing knowledge sharing: towards a second wave of knowledge management. *Knowledge and process management*, 11(2), 81-92.
- Ibrahim, H., & Zulkafli, A. (2016). Corporate governance, HRM practices and organizational performance. *Socio-Economic Problems and the State*. 14 (1), 30- 40.
- Iscan, O.F., Ersari, G., & Naktiyok, A. (2014). Effect of Leadership Style on Perceived Organizational Performance and Innovation: The Role of Transformational Leadership beyond the Impact of Transactional Leadership – An Application among Turkish SME's. *Procedia - Social and Behavior Behavioural Sciences*, 150, 881–889.
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behavior behaviour. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(3), 287-302.
- Jiang, J. Y., & Liu, C. W. (2015). High performance work systems and organizational effectiveness: The mediating role of social capital. *Human Resource Management Review*, 25(1), 126-137.
- Kaplan, R. S. and D.P. Norton (1996) Using the Balanced Scorecard as a Strategic Management System. *Harvard Business Review* (January-February), 75-85.
- Karatepe, O. M. (2016) Does job embeddedness mediate the effects of coworker and family support on creative performance? An empirical study in the hotel industry, *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 15:2, 119-132.
- Katz, D., & Kahn, R. L. (1978). Organizations and the system concept. *Classics of organization theory*, 80, 480.
- Kheng, Y. K., June, S., & Mahmood, R. (2013). The determinants of innovative work behavior behaviour in the knowledge intensive business services sector in Malaysia. *Asian Social Science*, 9(15), 47.
- Lambe, C. J., Wittmann, C. M., & Spekman, R. E. (2001). Social exchange theory and research on business-to-business relational exchange. *Journal of business-to-business marketing*, 8(3), 1-36.
- Leana, C. R., & Van Buren, H. J. (1999). Organizational social capital and employment practices. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 538-555.
- Lee, T. W., Mitchell, T. R., Sablinski, C. J., Burton, J. P., & Holtom, B. C. (2004). The effects of job embeddedness on organizational citizenship, job performance, volitional absences, and voluntary turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47, 711–722
- Leong, C. T., & Rasli, A. (2014). The Relationship between innovative work behaviour on work role performance: An empirical study. *Procedia-Social and Behavior Behavioural Sciences*, 129, 592-600.
- Lev, S., & Koslowsky, M. (2012). On-the-job embeddedness as a mediator between conscientiousness and school teachers' contextual performance. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 21(1), 57-83.
- Lorsch, J.W., (1970). Introduction to the structural design of organizations. *Organizational Structure and Design*, 1-16.

- Lupton, T., *Organizational Behavior Behaviour and Performance*, 1977, London: The Macmillan Press.
- Miller, D. (1983). The Correlates of Entrepreneurship in Three Types of Firms. *Management Science*, 29(7), 770-791.
- Mitchell, T. R., Holtom, B. C., Lee, T. W., Sablinski, C. J., & Erez, M. (2001). Why people stay: Using job embeddedness to predict voluntary turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44, 1102–1121.
- Mitchell, T. R., Holtom, B. C., Lee, T. W., Sablinski, C. J., & Erez, M. (2001). Why people stay: Using job embeddedness to predict voluntary turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(6), 1102-1121.
- Mukherjee, S. B., & Ray, A. (2009). Innovative work behavior/behaviour of managers: Implications regarding stressful challenges of modernized public-and private-sector organizations. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal*, 18(2), 101-107.
- Mura, M., Lettieri E., Spiller, N., & Radaelli, G. (2012). Intellectual capital and innovative work behavior/behaviour: opening the black box. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 4(39), 1-10.
- Murphy Jr, E. F., Gordon, J. D., & Mullen, A. (2004). A preliminary study exploring the value changes taking place in the United States since the September 11, 2001 terrorist attack on the World Trade Center in New York. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 50(1), 81-96.
- Nafei, W. (2015). The Effects of Job Embeddedness on Organizational Cynicism and Employee Performance: A Study on Sadat City University. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 6(1), 8-25.
- Nahapiet, J., & Ghoshal, S. (1998). Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organizational advantage. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(2), 242-266.
- Naveed, R. T., Alhaidan, H., Al Halbusi, H., & Al-Swidi, A. K. (2022). Do organizations really evolve? The critical link between organizational culture and organizational innovation toward organizational effectiveness: Pivotal role of organizational resistance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(2), 100178.
- Ng, D.C.; Law, K. (2015). Impacts of informal networks on innovation performance: Evidence in Shanghai. *Chin. Manag. Stud.*, 9, 56–72.
- Ng, T. W., & Feldman, D. C. (2010). The impact of job embeddedness on innovation-related behavior/behaviours. *Human Resource Management*, 49(6), 1067-1087.
- Ng, T. W., Feldman, D. C., & Lam, S. S. (2010). Psychological contract breaches, organizational commitment, and innovation-related behavior/behaviours: a latent growth modeling approach. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(4), 744-751.
- Nielsen, T. M., Hrivnak, G. A., & Shaw, M. (2009). Organizational citizenship behavior/behaviour and performance: A meta-analysis of group-level research. *Small Group Research*, 40, 555- 577.
- Noefer, K., Stegmaier, R., Molter, B. & Sonntag, K. (2009). A great many things and not a minute to spare: Can feedback from supervisors moderate in relationship between skill variety, time pressure, and employee's innovative behaviour. *Creativity Research Journal*, 21 (4), 384– 393.
- Oh, H., Labianca, G., & Chung, M. H. (2006). A multilevel model of group social capital. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(3), 569-582.
- Ostrom, E. (1975). *On Evaluating the Effectiveness, Responsiveness, Equity, and Efficiency of Police Organizational Arrangements in Metropolitan Areas*. Workshop in Political Theory and Policy Analysis. Indiana University.
- Pil, F. K., & Leana, C. (2009). Applying organizational research to public school reform: The effects of teacher human and social capital on student performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(6), 1101-1124.

- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavior-behavioural research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879-890.
- Pratikno, R., Purba, J. T., Bernarto, I., Sudibjo, N., & Pramono, R. (2021). Organizational Learning Capability The Mediating Between National Culture And Organizational Innovation: The Case Of Indonesian Universities In Greater Jakarta. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20, 1-15.
- Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2004). SPSS and SAS procedures for estimating indirect effects in simple mediation models. *Behavior Behaviour Research Methods*, 36(4), 717-731.
- Rass, M., Dumbach, M., Danzinger, F., Bullinger A.C. & Moeslein, K.M., (2013). Open Innovation and Firm Performance: The Mediating Role of Social Capital. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 22(2), 177-194.
- Scott, S.G. and Bruce, R.A. (1994) Determinants of Innovative Behavior Behaviour: A Path Model of Individual Innovation in the Workplace. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38, 1442-65.
- Scott, S.G. and Bruce, R.A. (1998) Following the Leader in R&D: The Joint Effect of Subordinate Problem-Solving Style and Leader-Member Relations on Innovative Behavior Behaviour. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 45, 3-10.
- Sekiguchi, T., Burton, J. P., & Sablinski, C. J. (2008). The role of job embeddedness on employee performance: The interactive effects with leader-member exchange and organization-based self-esteem. *Personnel Psychology*, 61, 761-792. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2008.00130.x>.
- Smith, J.E.P., & Blum, T.C. (2000). Work-family Human Resource Bundles and perceived organizational performance. *Academic of Management Journal*, 43(6), 1107-1117.
- Sözbilir, F. (2018). The interaction between social capital, creativity and efficiency in organizations. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 27, 92-100.
- Sumarna, A. D., & Muzakir, W. P. (2022). Non-Financial Factors Affecting Financial Performance in Indonesian NCSR Award Recipient Companies. *Berkala Akuntansi dan Keuangan Indonesia*, 7(1), 01-20.
- Sun, T., Zhao, X. W., Yang, L. B., & Fan, L. H. (2011). The impact of psychological capital on job embeddedness and job performance among nurses: A structural equation approach. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 68(1), 69-79.
- Tatar, E.L. (2011). The Importance of Measuring Individual Performance to Increase Organizational Performance. *Journal of Defense Resources Management*, 1, 113-118.
- Tsai, W. & Ghoshal, S. (1998). Social Capital and Value Creation: The Role of Intra-firm Networks. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(4), 464-478.
- Venkatraman, N., & Ramanujam, V. (1986). Measurement of business performance in strategy research: a comparison of approaches. *Academy of Management Review*, 1(4), 801-814.
- Wheeler, A. R., Harris, K. J., & Sablinski, C. J. (2012). How do employees invest abundant resources? The mediating role of work effort in the job-embeddedness/job-performance relationship. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42, E244-E266.
- Widianto, S., Abdullah, R., Kautsar, A. P., & Meiyanti, S. (2012). The effect of job embeddedness on work engagement and innovative behavior-behaviour. *Available at SSRN 2180736*.
- Wijayanto, B. R. & Kismono, G. (2004). The Effect of Job Embeddedness on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Behaviour: Mediating Role of Sense of Responsibility. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 6(3), 335-354.
- William Lee, T., Burch, T. C., & Mitchell, T. R. (2014). The story of why we stay: A review of job embeddedness. *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psychol. Organ. Behav.*, 1(1), 199-216.

- Xerri, M. & Brunetto, Y. (2011). Fostering the Innovative Behaviour of SME Employees: A Social Capital Perspective, *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 19(2), 43-59.
- Yao, L. H., Jiang, Y. M., Shi, J., Tomas-Barberan, F. A., Datta, N., Singanusong, R., & Chen, S. S. (2004). Flavonoids in food and their health benefits. *Plant foods for human nutrition*, 59(3), 113-122.
- Yi-Renko, H., Autio, E. and Sapienza, H. J. (2001). Social Capital, Knowledge Acquisition and Knowledge Exploitation in Young Technology-based Firms, *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(6), 587-613.
- Yli-Renko, H.; Sapienza, H.J.; Hay, M. (2001). The role of contractual governance flexibility in realizing the outcomes of key customer relationships. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16, 529–555.
- Yuan, F., & Woodman, R. W. (2010). Innovative behavior in the workplace: The role of performance and image outcome expectations. *Academy of management journal*, 53(2), 323-342.
- Zhang, X., & Bartol, K. M. (2010). Linking empowering leadership and employee creativity: The influence of psychological empowerment, intrinsic motivation, and creative process engagement. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(1), 107-128.